

CREATION OF SOCIETY

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Editorial:

Eudoxia Research Centre advocates the research and innovation by systematically developing a new model of multidisciplinary research. The conceptual developments of research, design and generation of solution to the existing research problem will influence the adoption of new research methodology and extraordinary output for “Creation of Society”. However this concept of conducting the multidisciplinary world summit titled “ World Summit on Social Sciences and Humanities 2020: SOSH” is influences researchers and academicians for combining their ideas into a single framework and combining the diversified research output to a single outcome of research as their joint work in this “Creation of Society”.

The primary objective of this summit was to receive the contributions from the field of social sciences and humanities for developing dynamic ideas for the future society, so that researchers can further identify, conceptualize and understand underlying theories of social sciences and humanities to find out the research gap for their future research and innovation. Rapid advances in the field of social sciences and humanities have profound implications for developing the global economy as well as the society at large. The selective papers in this book “Creation of Society” have the potential to directly influence both the society and scientific development to develop new research ethics for global researchers. Publication of this type of articles and research papers by the global academicians and researchers will shape the development and the diffusion of multidisciplinary research for building and understanding of different potential researchers especially from the field of social sciences and humanities. This work has potential impact of advances in social sciences and humanities research to identify the role and policy providing effective motivation for innovation in social sciences, humanities and other related areas.

This book can be positioned at the intersection of fiction and non-fiction writing in research with a new trajectory of idea to establish new facts and findings in research by influencing the digital innovation. Some of the papers presented a theoretical prospective with a value based model of social sciences and humanities research emphasizing the multilayered vibrant way of recent trends in research. On the other hand, practical application of social sciences and humanities are currently attracting a lot of attention for developing new phenomenon

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APPLICATION OF AHIMSA FOR THE WORLD BASED ON INDIAN PHILOSOPHY AND GANDHIAN PHILOSOPHY.

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Abstract:

Ahimsa or non-violence has formed part and parcel of Indian spirituality. It forms the core of Jain, Buddhist and Vedic Philosophy particularly. Gandhiji applied this concept of Ahimsa for political freedom of India through peaceful protest, demonstration and means. Clearly if we explore we can find further application of this beautiful concept of Ahimsa. This include political, social, economic etc. This concept can be applied in our education system. It can be used to reduce the incident of crime, terrorism etc. It has application in our environment. The application of Ahimsa can yield many positive results and hence its application should be understood and explored. It may hold the key to a peaceful world and many positive changes.

Keywords :- Ahimsa, Jainism, Crime, Education

INTRODUCTION:

The word Ahimsa has come from the root himsa or harm and the opposite of it is Ahimsa which means to cause no harm. Ahimsa has formed part and parcel of Indian Philosophy or Spiritualisms. It is at the crux of our cultural, spiritual philosophy and is deeply embedded in our DNA or genes. This primarily is the reason a number of Indians are Vegetarian, we believe in the concept of Athithi Devo Bhava. We have never attacked any country and for a long time we had no first use nuclear deterrent policy. India has seen votaries or champions of Ahimsa which include Mahatma Gandhi, Gautama Buddha, Mahavira, Vinobha Bhave, Baba Amte, Acharya Tulsi, Acharya Mahapragnya, Maharishi Patanjali. The Jain saints take the vow of non-violence and do not harm even insects intentionally. Ahimsa or non-violence can be of three types Manasik (Mentally), Kayik(Physical) or Vaceik (Verbal).In India we can have a huge section of people were vegetarianism. It is quite common to see worship of stones, animals, rivers, fire , air, tress. This clearly shows the concept of Ahimsa in our culture. Ahimsa as seen above age old traditions in our culture. We need to understand what can be the scope and extent of this Ahimsa in an applied form in the present day context. But Ahimsa is not something absolute. In Bhagwat Gita Krishna clearly says we must not be silent to injustice, or just be silent to evil forces. They have to be fought. The Bhagwat Gita gives the concept of soul, the eternal or indestructible nature of soul and destructible nature of human body or anything material. Hence, lord Krishna says not to grief on the body and do his body. According to Him the body is subjected is to birth, death and rebirth. But the soul is ageless, timeless. The Bhagwat Gita keeps us a clear understanding of duty. It asks us to do our duty established in our soul, established in divine consciousness – in, having full control on our senses and mind, a spirit of surrender to the almighty. It also asks us to do our duty established in our discrimination and without considering the results thereof. Duty should be done without attachment or desire and in the spirit of devotion. Even Mahatma Gandhi did not consider Ahimsa as absolute. He said if he had to select between violence and cowardice he would rather select violence. So his

concept of non-violence like the Bhagwat Gita too was not absolute.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

The objective of our study is to show that Ahimsa is an age old, timeless tradition in India. It exists as a theoretical, philosophical, spiritual concept etc. It has formed the crux of Buddhist and Jain Philosophy. For example Jainism believes in the concept Ahimsa Paramo Dhama that is Ahimsa is the highest form of spirituality. At the root of this philosophy lies the concept that every being has a right to life and since we can't give life to anyone. The concept of Ahimsa has been followed by the religious followers.

But the concept of Ahimsa we believe is extremely valuable to be restricted to a religious group or followers and has wider applications. Mahatma Gandhi used it in ensuring India's political freedom. In a similar way this concept of Ahimsa can be applied in a variety of field and we are trying to explore it in our paper. It can be said to be applied Ahimsa in a way. The paper is as such qualitative and exploratory in nature

LITERATURE REVIEW

- ▶ Education about non-violence helps to counter a culture of non-violence. One of the reasons there is so much violence in the postmodern world is that people neither understand nor appreciate the power of nonviolence. Nonviolence promotes empathy and helps students become compassionate towards the suffering of others at a personal level, Students should learn in schools how to resolve conflicts nonviolently. ¹
- ▶ For the Hindu the universe is God's body, of which we humans, along with everything else in nature, are but a part. The essence of earth, air, water, the tree, cow, you and me is the same divine spirit manifesting in different forms. Therefore it is natural that

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the ethic of radical non-violence (ahimsa:) to all forms of human, animal and plant life should have originated in India ⁱⁱ

- ▶ A close link or correlation was found in this study between violence, substance abuse and Mental illness ⁱⁱⁱ
- ▶ The study finds a close correlation between horror violent films video games and violent films during childhood and delinquency at age 14^{iv}
- ▶ The results of this study indicate that a school-based prevention approach previously found to prevent tobacco, alcohol, and illicit drug use can also prevent violence and delinquency.^v
- ▶ In political communication, nonviolence can be contrasted with rational dialogue, electoral politics and violence, and stands out from them in combining high transformative potential with dialogue and participation.^{vi}

APPLICATIONS:

Anna Hazara also tried to use this concept of Ahimsa to remove corruption from our political life. Nelson Mandela used it to drive Apartheid from South Africa. Nelson Mandela was deeply inspired by Mahatma Gandhi. But the application of Ahimsa has been limited in comparison to the vast potential that it has. Ahimsa can have a big role in ensuring a peaceful world order.

It can be used to reduce crimes from our society, drug abuse, social and domestic harmony etc. It can be used for water preservation, wastage of food, wastage of time, wastage of energy and effort, driving away sloth from society and individuals, work towards nation building, raising the standards of human life. Ahimsa should not be simply a philosophical or ideological thought but should emerge out of love or transform into love for mother earth or universal love for God's creation. Social and economic inequality, unemployment, poverty,

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illiteracy, child labor, human trafficking all falls in the ambit of Ahimsa. Martin Luther King after reading Gandhi said his skepticism concerning the power of love gradually diminished, and he came to see for the first time its potency in the area of social reform. He also talks about Gandhi's satyagraha or truth force or love force as he understood it and was widely influenced by it. He further adds it was Gandhi's philosophy of love and non-violence that he discovered the method of social reform.^{vi}

The concept of Ahimsa as given in Indian spirituality can help raise humanity to a new level. It can help conserve the ecology, environment, social harmony, individual and family well being, communal harmony, political peace and world peace. Ahimsa can have application in our educational system, legal, judicial, criminal system, economic and industrial issues etc. Gandhiji used Ahimsa as a tool for India's Political freedom.

The concept of Ahimsa can be applied to protect our borders, to nuclear weapons for self-protection for example like taekwondo in self-defense. It is important in the principle of construction of nuclear weapons, surgery in medical profession, killing of terrorist. In this way we can apply the concept of Ahimsa in totality. The Bhagwat Gita gives us a clear understanding of duty. It asks us to do our duty established in our soul, established in divine consciousness – in, having full control on our senses and mind, a spirit of surrender to the almighty. It also asks us to do our duty established in our discrimination and without considering the results thereof. Duty should be done without attachment or desire and in the spirit of devotion.

Ahimsa can have another dimension which can include Yoga, meditation etc. Yoga is the integration of mental, physical and spiritual wellbeing. Maharishi Patanjali gives us the concept of Ahimsa in Yama, Niyama. There are five aspects of Yama – Satya, Ahimsa, Brahmacharya, Asteya, Aparigraha. Ahimsa forms the bedrock or foundation of Yoga. Without the concept of Ahimsa the concept of peace and harmony in Yogic text can never become reality. Actual transformation has to take place at the level of mind. Violence lies in

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the mind, in our thought and this gets transformed in the actions. So at the root is transforming the mind, cutting down desires, attachments. The mind which have deep and subtle imprints of violence, anger, irritability, impatience, selfishness has to be filled with love, harmony, kindness, patience, sacrifice etc. Maharishi Patanjali in his Yoga Sutra says, "Ahimsa Pratishthaya Vaira Tyaga" that is wherever Ahimsa is established, conflict ends and peace reigns. If we see the life of Gautama Buddha we can clearly see how people like Angulimala, Emperor Ashoka gave up violence in the nonviolent, benevolent shade of Gautama. Ashoka believed that the entire country could be ruled on Buddhist principles. Vietnamese Zen master^{viii} Thich Nhat Hanh has worked in Northamerica and Europe teaching new ways of peace through Buddhist principle. He believed in world peace more than individual serenity. Peace he says is not simply the absence of violence; it is the cultivation of understanding, insight and compassion, combined with action. Being mindful is diminishing violence each day. Violence has taken deep roots within in the way we think, speak, and act. We can take a strong determination to live mindfully to live in peace.^{ix} SN Goenka who preached Vipassana in the Buddhist tradition of mindfulness meditation has contributed vastly to the cause of non-violence and peaceful living. The challenge is to imbibe Non-violence in our educational system. Constructive discussion, deliberation, team work rather than agitation, violent protest, peaceful protest etc. Anger and dominance cannot be allowed to have the way. In recent times we have seen violence across the globe including India and led by students, Universities. Such violence has led to destruction of public property and loss of precious human life. A program called Responding in Peaceful and positive (RIPP) ways was found to be extremely useful in preventing youth violence. It is a program designed for prevention of violence among school student middle and junior. Ripp is a program designed to control violence among students by an introduction of Team building activities, problem solving model, relaxation technique, social skills for violence prevention, conflict resolution skills, working with peer groups, in experimental setting, in stimulation setting, learning the cause and effect relationship and positive outcomes of the Ripp program was noticed among students.^v Ahimsa can be applied in

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the field of terrorism, racial prejudice. Religious fundamentalism often lies at the root of terrorism. People especially young people are misled by false religious doctrines, fundamentalist teachings. An effort should be made to reach out to the religious leaders and seek their help/influence in curbing such tendencies. Even religious prejudice, fundamentalism, religious discrimination, intolerance, caste based discrimination etc can also be considered a form of violence.

Ahimsa can also be applied in the field of mental psychological disorders, psychiatric disorders etc. We can see rising cases of psychological problems and at it roots lies violence, disorganization, domestic violence, relationship issues, anger, stress, behavior related problems, anti-social behavior etc. These problems are seen in children too in the form of disease like ADHD attention deficit hyperactive syndrome. In psychological disorders three scenarios can exist violence can exist or present as an outcome of a psychological disorder, second it can result in a disorder, third there can be strong correlation and in some cases no relation

Environment or Ecology is that humans have misused a lot, damaged beyond repair, inflicted tremendous violence on it. We have never been mindful to environmental or on our own actions which harm the environment. Here too non-violence has important applications and mindfulness can hold the key. Jinsena is his Adipurana have stated that the determination of man's social life was often guided by his environment. Contemporary environmental thinkers have felt that life is interconnected and suggested it as a foundation for environmental ethic. Scholars of Jain Philosophy see solution in it for correcting ecological imbalance through application of Ahimsa.^{xi}

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion we can say that Ahimsa as a theoretical knowledge, as a spiritual tradition and as a culture has remained in India for time immemorial. Its imprints can be seen in subtle aspects of our life. But in recent times its relevance and need has increased a lot. And its applications need to expand and cover wider aspect of our life including

crime, education, environment, social life, family, global order, political life and health. It holds the key to a peaceful order. The growing violence, agitations, environmental degradation has necessitated its need. Education must shape our conduct, our behavior, give us a balanced mindset and must fill our heart with peace and love. It is said education is for life and not living. People like Mahatma Gandhi, Martin Luther King, Nelson Mandela, Buddha showed us the way and now we need to find ways to walk the path. A mindfulness and conservation approach towards environment and ecology is required. We cannot destroy it indiscriminately. Criminal tendencies need to be transformed through love and nonviolence into love and peace. Non-violence is not absolute and depends on circumstances. However, non-violence is not weakness, infact it is inner strength, belief, fearlessness and self-control

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